

DATABASE:

*A2.1.1: Update EMPIR 20NRM02
MFMET database on sensors and
actuators*

Work package 2

2025-12-11

<https://mfmet.eu>

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Activity number	Activity description	Participants (Lead in bold)
A2.1.1 M6	METU with the support from INESC MN, Micronit, IPQ, CEA, LNEC, and microfluidic will update EMPIR 20NRM02 MFMET database/inventory regarding sensors and actuators used in microfluidic devices. Inputs can be base operating principles, active materials, dimensions, on-chip/off-chip, connection type, ranges, resolution for data acquisition/signal sending, as examples. The information will be used in A3.1.1. (by M3)	METU , INESC MN, Micronit, IPQ, CEA, LNEC, microfluidic

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1. Database on Sensors and Actuators

This document presents a comprehensive database of commercially available sensors and actuators that are suitable for use in microfluidic systems. The database has been developed to support researchers, engineers, and developers working in the fields of microfluidics, lab-on-chip technologies, organ-on-chip systems, and related disciplines.

The foundation of this compilation is the publicly available EMPIR 20NRM02 MFMET database for flow control components, accessible at: https://mfmet.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/2024.05.17_MFMET-Database-for-Flow-Control-Components.pdf. The present work expands upon that resource by integrating additional commercially available sensing and actuation components relevant to microfluidic applications.

The database includes a selection of actuator types such as flow generators, pressure-driven pumps, syringe pumps, peristaltic pumps, and piezoelectric diaphragm pumps. In terms of sensing technologies, it comprises flow sensors, pressure sensors, biosensors, oxygen (O₂) sensors, carbon dioxide (CO₂) sensors, and pH sensors. Each entry is accompanied by technical specifications and integration characteristics that facilitate their incorporation into microfluidic systems.

This extended dataset aims to provide a structured and up-to-date reference to assist in the design, implementation, and benchmarking of microfluidic platforms across a broad range of scientific and industrial contexts.

Flow Generators

Working Principle	Range	Stability	Accuracy	Unit	Connection type	Connection size	Manufacturer	Model	
Peristaltic pumps	0.03	30		mL/min	Straight connector	0.25-2.06 mm ID tubing	Watson Marlow	400 FD/A	
Peristaltic pumps	0.2			mL/min	Straight connector	1.2 mm ID Tygon tubing	Aquatech Co	RP-Q1.2N-P20Z-DC3V	
Peristaltic pumps	0.45			mL/min	Straight connector	1.5 mm ID Silicone tubing	Aquatech Co	RP-Q1.5S-P45Z-DC3V	
Peristaltic pumps	0.2			mL/min	Straight connector	1.2 mm ID SWFT tubing	Aquatech Co	RP-Q1.2C-P20Z-DC3V	
Peristaltic pumps	0.5			mL/min	Straight connector	1.2 mm ID Tygon tubing	Aquatech Co	RP-QX1.2N-P50Z-DC3V	
Peristaltic pumps	1.1			mL/min	Straight connector	1.5 mm ID Silicone tubing	Aquatech Co	RP-QX1.5S-1Z-DC3V	
Peristaltic pumps	0.5			mL/min	Straight connector	1.2 mm ID SWFT tubing	Aquatech Co	P-QX1.2C-P50Z-DC3V	
Peristaltic pumps	10	150		µL/min	Straight connector		Jobst Technology	CPP-1 150	
Peristaltic pumps	0.15	180		µL/min	Straight connector		Jobst Technology	CPP-1 180-ZM	
Peristaltic pumps	70	800		µL/min	Straight connector		Jobst Technology	CPP-1 800	
Peristaltic pumps	2	1700		µL/min	Straight connector		Jobst Technology	CPP-1 1000-ZM	
Piezoelectric diaphragm pump	0	14000		µL/min	Straight connector		Bartels Mikrotechnik	BP7	
Piezoelectric diaphragm pump	3			mL/h	Straight connector		Takasago	SDMP302	
Piezoelectric diaphragm pump	7			mL/h	Straight connector		Takasago	SDMP306	
Piezoelectric diaphragm pump	-200	300		mbar	Straight connector		The Lee Company	BL Series Disc Pump	
Piezoelectric diaphragm pump	-400	600		mbar	Straight connector		The Lee Company	HP Series Disc Pump	
Piezoelectric diaphragm pump	-220	270		mbar	Straight connector		The Lee Company	LT Series Disc Pump	
Piezoelectric diaphragm pump	-300	400		mbar	Straight connector		The Lee Company	XP Series Disc Pump	
Pressure controller	-1000	1000	0.007% FS	<0.5% FS	mbar	Fitting	UNF 10-32	Biophysical Tools	P ² CS Standard
Pressure controller	-200	4000	0.007% FS	<0.5% FS	mbar	Fitting	UNF 10-32	Biophysical Tools	P ² CS Plus
Pressure controller	-50	50	0.007% FS	<0.5% FS	mbar	Fitting	UNF 10-32	Biophysical Tools	P ² CS Levels
Pressure controller	-200	4000	0.007% FS	<0.5% FS	mbar	Fitting	UNF 10-32	Biophysical Tools	P ² CS Analogue
Pressure driven pump	0	25	0.1% MV	0.25% FS	mbar		Fluigent	Flow EZ LU-FEZ-0025	
Pressure driven pump	0	69	0.1% MV	0.25% FS	mbar		Fluigent	Flow EZ LU-FEZ-0069	
Pressure driven pump	0	345	0.1% MV	0.25% FS	mbar		Fluigent	Flow EZ LU-FEZ-0345	
Pressure driven pump	0	1000	0.1% MV	0.25% FS	mbar		Fluigent	Flow EZ LU-FEZ-1000	
Pressure driven pump	0	2000	0.1% MV	0.25% FS	mbar		Fluigent	Flow EZ LU-FEZ-2000	
Pressure driven pump	0	7000	0.1% MV	0.25% FS	mbar		Fluigent	Flow EZ LU-FEZ-7000	
Pressure driven pump	0	-25	0.1% MV	0.25% FS	mbar		Fluigent	Flow EZ LU-FEZ-N025	
Pressure driven pump	0	-69	0.1% MV	0.25% FS	mbar		Fluigent	Flow EZ LU-FEZ-N069	
Pressure driven pump	0	-345	0.1% MV	0.25% FS	mbar		Fluigent	Flow EZ LU-FEZ-N345	
Pressure driven pump	0	-800	0.1% MV	0.25% FS	mbar		Fluigent	Flow EZ LU-FEZ-N800	
Pressure driven pump	-900	2000	0.005% FS		mbar		Elveflow	OB1 MK4	
Pressure driven pump	-750	750			mbar	UNF 10-32	Biophysical Tools	PVS-750	
Pressure driven pump	-750	1500			mbar	UNF 10-32	Biophysical Tools	PVS-1500	
Pressure driven pump	-750	5000			mbar	UNF 10-32	Biophysical Tools	PVS-4000	
Pressure driven pump	0	2000		0.1	mbar	Quick connect	Elveflow	Cobalt	
Pressure driven pump	-700	1000		0.1	mbar	Quick connect	Elveflow	Cobalt-dual	
Pressure driven pump	-40	80			kPa		PreciGenome	Mini Microfluidic Pump	
Syringe pump			≤ 0.05 % CV	≤ 0.5 %		Fitting	¼ - 28" or M6	Tecan	Cavro XLP 6000
Syringe pump			≤ 0.05 % at full stroke	≤ 0.25 %		Fitting	¼ - 28" or M7	Tecan	Cavro Centris
Syringe pump			≤ 0.05 % at full stroke	≤ 1.0 % (1 ml syringe)		Fitting	1/4-28" or M6	Tecan	Cavro XCalibur
Syringe pump	0.73 (1 mL syringe)	2100000 (60 mL syringe)			µL/hr	Luer	New Era	NE-1000	
Syringe pump	0.000007 (0.5 µL syringe)	142260 (140 mL syringe)			µL/hr	Luer	New Era	NE-1002X	
Syringe pump	1.436 (1 mL syringe)	7515000 (60 mL syringe)			µL/hr	Luer	New Era	NE-4000 Two channel	
Syringe pump	1.733 (1 mL syringe)	340600 (140 mL syringe)			µL/hr	Luer	New Era	NE-8000	
Syringe pump	6.803 (1 mL syringe)	1021000 (140 mL syringe)			µL/hr	Luer	New Era	NE-8060	
Syringe pump	0.452 (1 mL syringe)	415900 (10 mL syringe)			µL/hr	Luer	New Era	NE-1800 Eight Channel	
Syringe pump	0.452 (1 mL syringe)	1451000 (60 mL syringe)			µL/hr	Luer	New Era	NE-1600 Six Channel	
Syringe pump	0.45 (1 mL syringe)	153200 (3 mL syringe)			µL/hr	Luer	New Era	NE-1200 Twelve Channel	
Syringe pump	1.6x10 ⁻⁸ (with 0.5 µL syringe)	15000 (140 mL syringe)		< 0.04%	µL/min	Luer	Chemxyx	Nexus 3000	
Syringe pump	3.01x10 ⁻⁹ (2.5 mL syringe)	400000 (100 mL syringe)			µL/min	Fitting or Luer-Lock	1/4"-28UNF female	Cetoni	Nemesis M

Syringe pump	8x10 ⁻⁹ (10 µL syringe)	300000 (50 mL syringe)		µL/min	Fitting or Luer-Lock	1/4"-28UNF female	Cetoni	Nemesys S
Syringe pump	0.1 (with 0.5 µL syringe)	157 (with 60 mL syringe)	< 0.35%	mL/min			KR Analytical	Fusion 100-X
Syringe pump	0.1 (with 0.5 µL syringe)	102 (with 60 mL syringe)	< 0.35%	mL/min			KR Analytical	Fusion 200-X
Syringe pump	0.1 (with 0.5 µL syringe)	170.5 (with 100 mL syringe)	< 0.35%	mL/min			KR Analytical	Fusion 4000-X
Syringe pump	0.1 (with 0.5 µL syringe)	408 (with 300 mL syringe)	< 0.35%	mL/min			KR Analytical	Fusion 6000-X
Syringe pump	1.28x10 ⁻⁶ (0.5 µL syringe)	88280 (60 mL syringe)	±0.5%	µL/min			Kd Scientific	Legato 100 infusion
Syringe pump	1.28x10 ⁻⁶ (0.5 µL syringe)	25990 (10 mL syringe)	±0.5%	µL/min			Kd Scientific	Legato 101 infusion
Syringe pump	1.28x10 ⁻⁶ (0.5 µL syringe)	88280 (60 mL syringe)	±0.5%	µL/min			Kd Scientific	Legato 110 infusion/withdrawal
Syringe pump	1.28x10 ⁻⁶ (0.5 µL syringe)	25990 (10 mL syringe)	±0.5%	µL/min			Kd Scientific	Legato 111 infusion/withdrawal
Syringe pump	3.66x10 ⁻⁶ (0.5 µL syringe)	3818 (1 mL syringe)	±0.5%	µL/min			Kd Scientific	Legato 130 infusion/withdrawal
Syringe pump	0.58x10 ⁻⁶ (0.5 µL syringe)	11700 (10 mL syringe)	±0.35%	µL/min			Kd Scientific	Legato 180 infusion/withdrawal
Syringe pump	0.54x10 ⁻⁶ (0.5 µL syringe)	39000 (60 mL syringe)	±0.35%	µL/min			Kd Scientific	Legato 185 infusion/withdrawal
Syringe pump	3.06x10 ⁻⁶ (0.5 µL syringe)	215800 (140 mL syringe)	±0.35%	µL/min			Kd Scientific	Legato 200 dual infusion
Syringe pump	3.06x10 ⁻⁶ (0.5 µL syringe)	215800 (140 mL syringe)	±0.35%	µL/min			Kd Scientific	Legato 210 dual infusion/withdrawal
Syringe pump	3.06x10 ⁻⁶ (0.5 µL syringe)	215800 (140 mL syringe)	±0.35%	µL/min			Kd Scientific	Legato 270 dual push/pull
Syringe pump	0.1x10 ⁻⁶ (0.5 µL syringe)	13249200 (140 mL syringe)	±0.35%	µL/min			Harvard Apparatus	PHD 22/2000
Syringe pump	1.02x10 ⁻⁶ (0.5 µL syringe)	106000 (60 mL syringe)	± 0.25%	µL/min			Harvard Apparatus	Pumps 33 DDS (Dual Drive System)
Syringe pump	1.26x10 ⁻⁶ (0.5 µL syringe)	88400 (60 mL syringe)	±0.5%	µL/min			Harvard Apparatus	Pump 11 Elite Single Syringe
Syringe pump	1.26x10 ⁻⁶ (0.5 µL syringe)	26020 (60 mL syringe)	±0.5%	µL/min			Harvard Apparatus	Pump 11 Elite Dual Syringe
Syringe pump	0.54x10 ⁻⁶ (0.5 µL syringe)	39770 (60 mL syringe)	±0.5%	µL/min			Harvard Apparatus	Pump 11 Pico Plus Single Syringe
Syringe pump	0.54x10 ⁻⁶ (0.5 µL syringe)	11700 (10 mL syringe)	±0.5%	µL/min			Harvard Apparatus	Pump 11 Pico Plus Dual Syringe
Syringe pump	1.56x10 ⁻⁶ (0.5 µL syringe)	216000 (140 mL syringe)	±0.25%	µL/min			Harvard Apparatus	PHD ULTRA
Syringe pump	3.06x10 ⁻⁶ (0.5 µL syringe)	216000 (140 mL syringe)	±0.35%	µL/min			Harvard Apparatus	PHD ULTRA 4400
Syringe pump	0.00717	8000	< 1%	µL/min	Fitting	1/4" 28 UNF	Advanced Microfluidics	LSPone HD - P110-L
Syringe pump	0.00745	30000	< 1%	µL/min	Fitting	1/4" 28 UNF	Advanced Microfluidics	LSPone P100-L
Syringe pump	0.373	150000	< 1%	µL/min	Fitting	1/4" 28 UNF	Advanced Microfluidics	LSPone+ P101-L
Syringe pump	0.359	40 000	< 1%	µL/min	Fitting	1/4" 28 UNF	Advanced Microfluidics	LSPone+ HD P111-L

Flow sensors

Working principle	Range		Accuracy	Resolution	Unit	Pressure rating	Connection type	Connection size	Manufacturer	Model
Coriolis mass flow meter	0	200	±0.2% MV		g/h	200 bar	Swagelok	6 mm	Bronkhorst	M12
Coriolis mass flow meter	0	2000	±0.2% MV		g/h	200 bar	Swagelok	6 mm	Bronkhorst	M13
Coriolis mass flow meter	0	200	±0.2% MV		g/h	200 bar	Swagelok	6 mm	Bronkhorst	ML120V00
Other	0	30	2% MV		µL/min		Fitting	1/4"-28 UNF	Microfluidics Innovation Center	Galileo I
Other	0	480	2% MV		µL/min		Fitting	1/4"-28 UNF	Microfluidics Innovation Center	Galileo II
Thermal sensor	0	80	5% (H ₂ O)		µL/min	50 bar	Fitting	1/4"-28 UNF	Sensiron	SLI-0430
Thermal sensor	0	16.6	5% (H ₂ O)		mL/min	3 bar	Fitting	1/4"-28 UNF	Sensiron	LD20-2600B
Thermal sensor	0	40	5% (H ₂ O)		mL/min	12 bar	Fitting	1/4"-28 UNF	Sensiron	SLS-1500
Thermal sensor	0	5	5% (H ₂ O)		mL/min	15 bar	Fitting	1/4"-28 UNF	Sensiron	SLI-2000
Thermal sensor	0	1	5% (H ₂ O)		mL/min	15 bar	Fitting	1/4"-28 UNF	Sensiron	SLI-1000
Thermal sensor	0	2	5% (H ₂ O)		mL/min	12 bar	Fitting	1/4"-28 UNF	Sensiron	SLF3S-0600F
Thermal sensor	0	1.5	±10% MV		µL/min		Fitting	1/4"-28 UNF	Elveflow	MFS1+
Thermal sensor	0	7	±5% MV		µL/min		Fitting	1/4"-28 UNF	Elveflow	MFS2+
Thermal sensor	0	80	±5% MV		µL/min		Fitting	1/4"-28 UNF	Elveflow	MFS3+
Thermal sensor	0	1	±5% MV		mL/min		Fitting	1/4"-28 UNF	Elveflow	MFS4+
Thermal sensor	0	5	±5% MV		mL/min		Fitting	1/4"-28 UNF	Elveflow	MFS5+
Thermal sensor	0	40	±5% MV		mL/min		Fitting	1/4"-28 UNF	Elveflow	MFS6+
Thermal sensor	0	500	±(2+0.5FS)%		mL/min	0.8 MPa	Fitting	1/4"-28 UNF	Siargo	LF3000
Thermal sensor	0	1.5	10% MV (H ₂ O)	3.7x10 ⁻³	µL/min	200 bar	Fitting	UNF 6-40 for 1/32" OD tubing	Fluigent	FLU-XS
Thermal sensor	0	7	5% MV (H ₂ O)	10x10 ⁻³	µL/min	201 bar	Fitting	UNF 6-40 for 1/32" OD tubing	Fluigent	FLU-S
Thermal sensor	0	2	5% MV (H ₂ O)	0.25x10 ⁻³	mL/min	12 bar	Fitting	UNF 1/4"-28 flat bottom for 1/16" OD tubing	Fluigent	FLU-M+
Thermal sensor	0	40	5% MV (H ₂ O)	25x10 ⁻³	mL/min	13 bar	Fitting	UNF 1/4"-28 flat bottom for 1/16" OD tubing	Fluigent	FLU-L+
Thermal sensor	0	7	5% MV (H ₂ O)	10x10 ⁻³	µL/min	200 bar	Fitting	UNF 6-40 for 1/32" OD tubing	Fluigent	FLU-S-D
Thermal sensor	0	80	5% MV (H ₂ O)	0.06	µL/min	100 bar	Fitting	UNF 6-40 for 1/32" OD tubing	Fluigent	FLU-M-D
Thermal sensor	0	1	5% MV (H ₂ O)	0.7x10 ⁻³	mL/min	15 bar	Fitting	Flangeless fitting 1/4-28	Fluigent	FLU-L-D
Thermal sensor	0	5	5% MV (H ₂ O)	3x10 ⁻³	mL/min	16 bar	Fitting	Flangeless fitting 1/4-28	Fluigent	FLU-XL
Thermal sensor	0	7	max (5% MV, 0.3 %FR)		µL/min	50 bar			PreciGenome	PG-LFS-0150
Thermal sensor	0	80	max (5% MV, 0.15 %FR)		µL/min	51 bar			PreciGenome	PG-LFS-0430
Thermal sensor	0	1000	max (5% MV, 0.2 %FR)		µL/min	52 bar			PreciGenome	PG-LFS-1000
Thermal sensor	0	5000	max (5% MV, 0.2 %FR)		µL/min	53 bar			PreciGenome	PG-LFS-2000
Thermal sensor	0	500	±(2.0+0.5FS)		mL/min		Fitting	UNF 1/4"-28 flat bottom	Siargo	LF3000 series

Pressure sensor

Working principle	Range		Accuracy	Resolution	Unit	Connection type	Connection size	Manufacturer	Model
other	-11.5	75	±5% MV		psi			PendoTECH	Single-use pressure sensor
other	-5	60	±0.3		psi	Luer or barbed		Parker Domnick Hunter	SciPres
other	0	16	2% FS		bar	Luer lock		Elveflow	Microfluidic inline pressure sensor - MFP
other	-345	345	2 to 3		mbar	Fitting	1/4"-28 Flat bottom	Fluigent	Pressure Unit S
other	-1000	1000	10 to 20		mbar	Fitting	1/4"-28 Flat bottom	Fluigent	Pressure Unit M
other	-1000	7000	16 to 40		mbar	Fitting	1/4"-28 Flat bottom	Fluigent	Pressure Unit XL
other	-1	1	±0.5% max range		psi	barbed (large pack), fitting (small pack)	3/32" ID (large pack) - 10-32 thread with ferrule	Elveflow	MPS0
other	-5	5	±2% max range		psi	barbed (large pack), fitting (small pack)	3/32" ID (large pack) - 10-32 thread with ferrule	Elveflow	MPS1
other	-15	15	±0.2% max range		psi	barbed (large pack), fitting (small pack)	3/32" ID (large pack) - 10-32 thread with ferrule	Elveflow	MPS2
other	-15	30	±0.2% max range		psi	barbed (large pack), fitting (small pack)	3/32" ID (large pack) - 10-32 thread with ferrule	Elveflow	MPS3
other	-15	100	±0.2% max range		psi	barbed (large pack), fitting (small pack)	3/32" ID (large pack) - 10-32 thread with ferrule	Elveflow	MPS4
other	0	250	1%		kPa	Captite™	360 µm OD capillary, 1/32" OD tubing, or 1/16" OD tubing	LabSmith	uPS0250
other	0	800	1%		kPa	Captite™	361 µm OD capillary, 1/32" OD tubing, or 1/16" OD tubing	LabSmith	uPS0800
quartz resonant	13.5	100	0.06% FS	0.001	psi	Fitting	1/4"-28 flat bottom	Phase sensors	XtalX µLUQS
other	50	500	±(2.0+0.8 FS)		Pa	V-nozzle		Siargo	FSP1000 series

O₂, CO₂ and pH sensors									
Working principle	Range		LOD	Resolution	Accuracy	Unit	Connector Type	Manufacturer	Model
Optical O ₂	0	45	15 ppb	± 0.005	±0.05% MV	mg/L	Male Mini Luer	PreSens	O2 SensorPlug
Optical O ₂	0	22	1%	1%		mg/L		Pyroscience	Oxnano nanoprobes and PICO-O ₂ readout
Optical pH	5.5	8.5		± 0.01	± 0.05	pH	Male Mini Luer	PreSens	pH SensorPlug
Optical CO ₂	10	250		±0.06% MV	± 5% MV	hPa pCO ₂	Male Mini Luer	PreSens	CO2 SensorPlug

Biosensors									
Working principle	Range		LOD	Resolution	Accuracy	Unit	Connector Type	Manufacturer	Model
Electrochemical glucose	0.05	25	-	-	-	mM	Luer lock	Innovative Sensor Technology	B.LV5 biosensor array (glucose and lactate)
Electrochemical lactate	0.02	15	-	-	-	mM	Luer lock	Innovative Sensor Technology	B.LV5 biosensor array (glucose and lactate)